
Supplementary Material for Data analysis from GSR and EEG wearable sensors with Orange data Mining and Viscovery SOMine

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SECTION 1. INTRODUCCION

This supplementary section provides an expanded methodological account of the study, addressing both the physiological and environmental data streams that can be acquired and analysed using wearables sensors. The content is organized into dedicated sections covering instruments, computational tools, the methodological workflow, and the presentation of supplementary results in both GSR and EEG datasets. The aim is to present a structured, reproducible, and academically rigorous narrative of the procedures applied. A complementary laboratory manual is available as well as an open-access resource [1], which provides step-by-step operational instructions, while the present document emphasizes conceptual logic, methodological rationale, and analytical outcomes.

Instruments

Data were acquired using a combination of wearable physiological and environmental sensors, complemented by dedicated EEG hardware. The following instruments were employed:

- Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) sensor (NEULOG) [2]: measured electrodermal activity as an index of sympathetic arousal.
- GPS sensor (NEULOG) [2]: provided geospatial positioning, enabling environmental and physiological measures to be contextualized geographically.
- Humidity sensor (NEULOG) [2]: recorded environmental relative humidity in real time.
- Emotiv EPOC X headset (Emotiv Inc., USA) [3]: a wireless EEG device with 14 channels of saline-based sensors, designed for mobile data acquisition in both laboratory and field contexts.

The combination of NEULOG sensors with the Emotiv EPOC X enabled multimodal acquisition of environmental, physiological, and neurophysiological data, extending the scope of the study beyond traditional laboratory settings.

Computational Tools

A set of software applications were employed to support preprocessing, data conversion, visualization, and advanced analysis:

- MyGeoData Cloud Converter [4]: used for transforming geospatial .kml files into .csv tables.
- Orange Data Mining [5]: an open-source platform with modular architecture for data import, inspection, integration, and geospatial visualization (via the Geo add-on).
- Viscosity SOMine [6]: commercial software implementing Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) [7], enabling the identification of latent structures within multimodal data.
- Spreadsheet software (Microsoft Excel, LibreOffice Calc): used for manual inspection, harmonization of variable names, and preliminary formatting.
- EmotivPRO (Emotiv Inc.) [3]: the proprietary software platform for the Emotiv EPOC X, used for EEG data visualization, recording management, and extraction of raw EEG signals into compatible formats for subsequent analysis.

Methodological Workflow

The methodological workflow was organized into six stages, reflecting the logical progression from raw data acquisition to advanced analysis:

- Stage 1. Data acquisition.
Wearable NEULOG sensors and the Emotiv EPOC X headset generated multimodal data streams. NEULOG devices exported data in .csv and .kml formats, while EmotivPRO enabled the extraction of EEG data from the EPOC X into tabular formats (csv) for compatibility with further processing.
- Stage 2. Data conversion and preprocessing.
NEULOG .kml files were converted into .csv using MyGeoData Cloud Converter [5]. EEG recordings extracted with EmotivPRO were saved in .csv format, containing raw voltage values per channel and the Fourier transform of the electroencephalogram. Preprocessing involved:
 - 1) Inspection of file completeness and integrity.
 - 2) Harmonization of variable names across modalities.
 - 3) Removal of corrupted or incomplete records.
 - 4) Adjustment of numeric formats and delimiters.
 - 5) Normalization of continuous variables prior to unsupervised analysis.
- Stage 3. Data integration.
Preprocessed files were imported into Orange [2]. The Data Table widget enabled inspection of structures, while irrelevant variables were excluded with Select Columns. Datasets from different NEULOG sensors were merged using Merge Data, creating a unified dataset. EEG data, while available, were only partially integrated at this stage, as described in the EEG-specific section below.

- Stage 4. Geospatial visualization.
Orange's Geo Map widget was used for mapping GSR and humidity values. Latitude and longitude were manually assigned. Circle color intensity represented GSR, while circle size represented humidity (figure 1). Different map backgrounds were tested for clarity.

Figure 1: Geospatial representation integrating GSR and humidity.
Source: the authors.

- Stage 5. Exploratory analysis with Self-Organizing Maps.
Data were exported to Viscosity SOMine [4]. The SOM algorithm projected multidimensional data into a two-dimensional lattice [3]. Variables were normalized, and missing values removed prior to analysis. Outputs included component planes and cluster maps, which revealed associations between GSR and humidity.
- Stage 6. Integration of multimodal results.
Geospatial representations and SOM outputs were examined jointly to identify convergent patterns across methods. This integration enhanced interpretability, providing both spatial and abstract representations of the relationships detected in the data (figure 2).

*Figure 2: Data analysis by Self Organizing Maps, using Orange Data Mining Software
Source: the authors.*

SECTION 2. DATA ANALYSIS OF WEARABLE SENSORS GSR TYPE WITH ORANGE DATA MINING

The geospatial analysis demonstrated systematic patterns linking environmental and physiological data. Specifically, regions characterized by low humidity corresponded to lower GSR responses. Such associations, while preliminary, underscore the potential of combined geospatial and physiological analyses in detecting context-dependent patterns.

The SOM analysis provided additional insight by revealing clusters not identifiable through descriptive visualization alone. These clusters suggested that specific environmental conditions were associated with characteristic GSR profiles. The approach demonstrates the added value of combining unsupervised learning with geospatial visualization in the interpretation of multimodal sensor datasets.

SECTION 3. DATA ANALYSIS OF EEG WEARABLE SENSOR WITH VISCOVERY SOMINE

EEG data were recorded using the Emotiv EPOC X headset. Recordings were managed and exported through EmotivPRO. The extracted files contained raw electrical potentials from 14 channels in .csv format.

The raw EEG values were inspected for structural consistency and completeness, and prepared for loading into Viscovery SOMine. Figures illustrating EEG data import and preliminary visualization are referenced in the original supplementary material (figure 3).

*Figure 3: EEG data visualization by Self Organizing Maps, using Viscovery SOMine Software
Source: the authors.*

Analyses of EEG data require advanced preprocessing and feature extraction. However, in this supplementary material, only their recording, extraction, and preparation steps are described.

SECTION 4. REFERENCES

- [1] Author names and DOI have been removed to ensure the anonymity of the review process.
- [2] NEULOG, Wearable Sensor Ecosystem. [Online]. Available: <https://neulog.com>
- [3] Emotiv Inc., Emotiv EPOC X and EmotivPRO Software. [Online]. Available: <https://www.emotiv.com>
- [4] MyGeoData, Online GIS Data Converter. [Online]. Available: <https://mygeodata.cloud/converter>
- [5] J. Demšar, T. Curk, A. Erjavec, Č. Gorup, T. Hočevar, M. Milutinovič, M. Možina, M. Polajnar, M. Toplak, A. Starič, M. Štajdohar, L. Umek, L. Žagar, J. Žbontar, M. Žitnik, & Blaž Zupan, “Orange: Data Mining Toolbox in Python,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 14, pp. 2349–2353, 2013.
<https://www.jmlr.org/papers/v14/demsar13a.html>
- [6] Viscovery Software GmbH, Viscovery SOMine. [Online]. Available: <https://www.viscovery.net>
- [7] T. Kohonen, *Self-Organizing Maps*, 3rd ed., Springer Series in Information Sciences, vol. 30. Berlin, Germany: Springer, 2001.